

Spectrophotometric Determination of Nickel with Rubeanic Acid in Presence of Quinoline, α -Picoline and Collidine

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Ni(II) forms a bluish-violet coloured complex in presence of alcoholic solution of rubeanic acid and one of the heterocyclic bases viz., quinoline, α -picoline and collidine. The system shows maximum absorption at 390 nm and obeys Beer's law in the pH range 7.5 to 9.

THE bluish-violet colour developed by Ni(II) ion in presence of rubeanic acid solution and one of the heterocyclic bases, quinoline, α -picoline or collidine, was found to be more sensitive than the one obtained in the Ni(II)-rubeanic acid pyridine system described by Xavier and Ray¹.

The colour reaction of each of the three systems has been studied spectrophotometrically. The bluish-violet colour developed is found to absorb maximally at 390 nm. The optimal pH range is 7.5 to 9 in each of the three systems where Beer's law is obeyed. The reactions are more sensitive compared to the Ni(II)-rubeanic acid-pyridine system.

A comparative result of the detailed spectrophotometric studies including effects of diverse ions, composition of the complexes, Ringbom's plot and Beer's law are furnished in the paper.

Experimental

Chemicals, reagents and apparatus: Nickel chloride (G.R.) was dissolved in double distilled water and standardised gravimetrically using dimethyl glyoxime reagent. Rubeanic acid solution (0.1%) was prepared in 90% ethyl alcohol. The solution remains stable for several days. 10% solutions of freshly distilled quinoline, α -picoline or collidine in distilled alcohol were used for all determinations. Solutions of other cations and anions were obtained from analytical grade reagents.

Absorbance measurements were made with Hilger-UVispck spectrophotometer and pH values were determined with Elico Model L1-10 pH meter, the values being with respect to aqueous alcoholic solution.

Absorbance curves: The bluish-violet coloured solution of nickel rubeanate developed with the addition to nickel(II) solution 10 times its weight of rubeanic acid and varying amounts of the three bases, 4 ml in case of quinoline, 2 ml in case of α -picoline and 1 ml in case of collidine (optimal amounts) showed maximum absorbance in the regions 390 nm and 570-590 nm against a reagent blank.

All subsequent measurements were made at any of the regions having maximum absorbance. Though two sets of absorption maxima are observed in the case of the mixed ligand complexes of quinoline, α -picoline or collidine, the trend and nature of shifting remains the same.

Effect of pH, reagent and time: Effect of pH was studied with Ni(II) solutions containing 3.75 μ g of Ni(II)/ml, 1 ml of rubeanic acid solution and varying amounts of the heterocyclic bases (as stated for absorbance curves) in a final volume of 25 ml. The measurement was made in 90% alcoholic medium. The pH was in the alkaline region from 7.5 to 9.

1 ml of 0.1% (w/v) solution of rubeanic acid was found to be sufficient for an amount of nickel within the range 3.75 ppm to 4.40 ppm for the three different bases. Higher reagent concentration had no effect on colour intensity.

The system was stable up to 1 hr of preparation of solution but not longer.

Beer's law and optimum range: The nickel-rubeanic acid-quinoline and α -picoline systems were found to obey Beer's law over the ranges of 0.625 ppm to 4.375 ppm of Ni(II). The optimum working range from Ringbom's curve was found to be 1.3 ppm to 4.4 ppm of Ni(II). The nickel-rubeanic acid-collidine system was found to obey Beer's law over the ranges 0.625 ppm to 3.75 ppm of Ni(II). The optimum concentration range ascertained from Ringbom's curve lies within 1.2 ppm to 3.7 ppm.

Molar-extinction coefficient and sensitivity: The sensitivity and consequently molar extinction coefficient of mixed ligand complexes of nickel are also much greater than those of the individual complexes with rubeanic acid or aromatic base. None of the studied systems has got special advantage over others. From the stand point of sensitivity, the most effective aromatic base for nickel-rubeanic acid system is quinoline followed by collidine and α -picoline in decreasing order which shows that these do not strictly conform to the order of basicity of the second ligand. The results are shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1—THE RELATIVE SENSITIVITIES OF THE SYSTEMS

Metal ion	Reagents	Sandell's sensitivity	Molar extinction coefficient
Ni ²⁺	Rubeanic acid and quinoline	0.0068 $\mu\text{g Ni/cm}^2$	8457
Ni ²⁺	Rubeanic acid and α -picoline	0.0076 $\mu\text{g Ni/cm}^2$	7671
Ni ²⁺	Rubeanic acid and collidine	0.0071 $\mu\text{g Ni/cm}^2$	8221
Ni ²⁺	Rubeanic acid and pyridine	0.0128 $\mu\text{g Ni/cm}^2$	4571 (Xavier and Ray) ¹

Composition of the complexes : The composition of the complexes as determined by the Job's method of continued variation³ and by molar ratio method⁴, presents a divergent picture. While in the case of α -picoline, the metal : rubeanic acid ratio in the mixed ligand complex is 1 : 1, in the case of collidine, 1 : 2 ratio is obtained and in the complex system with quinoline, the nickel : rubeanic acid ratio is found to be 2 : 3. The study of the complex species in solid state by other workers showed a variety of the complexes having metal ligand ratio of 1 : 1⁵, 1 : 2⁶ and 2 : 3⁶. All these different species seem to have been stabilised by mixed ligation with different heterocyclic bases.

Effect of diverse ions : The effect of diverse ions was studied after the development of the colour with 2.5 ppm Ni(II) in presence of the ions whose effects were to be studied. The absorbance of the solutions was measured at 390 nm in each case. The tolerance limits for foreign ions for these three systems were alike. Molybdate, tungstate and vanadate did not interfere with nickel estimations up to 500 ppm. Tartrate, oxalate and citrate did not interfere up to 100 ppm. The Cu(II), Cd(II), Pb(II), Fe(III), Mn(II), Co(II), Pd(II), Al(III), Cr(III) and Bi(III) ions were found to interfere.

References

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